

Using Survival Analysis To Investigate Undergraduate Student Dropout Rates In The College Of Arts, Media And Technology, Chiang Mai University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Drop Out, Survival Analysis, Kaplan Meier, Cox Regression</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5570796</p>	<p><i>This research aims to study the survival function, the hazard rate for dropouts and the hazard function of students of the College of Art, Media and Technology, Chiang Mai University. The results of the study found that the highest dropout rates were for students in software engineering, 15 of which accounted for 31.25 percent. The lowest number of dropouts were from the digital game department with 3 students, accounting for 5 percent. For the life table, the software engineering department students had the highest dropout hazard rate of 0.18 which occurred during the first semester of the academic year 2017, but with an 83% chance of surviving longer than the first semester of the academic year 2017. The dropout rate was 17%, and the proportion of students surviving was 83%. The digital game department had the lowest hazard rate, 0.02. In addition, the median of the survival period of students in all 3 departments could not be found due to the dropout rate of students being less than 50%. That is, half of the students had not yet dropped out during the study period. The Kaplan Meier method of survival analysis and Log-Rank test analyzed with four independent variables: gender, department, parents' occupations and GPA. There was a statistically significant difference in survival function and survival analysis using Cox Regression. The variable most influencing student dropout hazard rate was GPA.</i></p>

Introduction

The education systems around the world have been changed by many factors which directly affect the input and output of university students (Bungau, C., et al., 2018). This problem is a serious issue that affects a country's education and economy, given the substantial investment in education made by national governments (Sandoval-Paliset, al., 2020). Reports from several studies indicate that university student's dropout rates are influenced by several factors or issues (Vossensteyn H., et al., 2015; National Statistical Institute of Norway, 2020; OECD, 2019).

The studies of factors or issues are the main points of consideration to see what is currently going on in education systems. Current studies measure educational output, which indicates educational quality, namely student desirable traits, satisfaction, morality and ethics. For dropouts, it was found that there was a greater interest in various entertainment media with less interest in education. Changing social conditions harm the development of education's goal to produce graduates with effective theoretical and practical knowledge in their work. Based on modern technology, it will be the cornerstone for the study of things that benefit society and give knowledge both within and outside the university. The findings were then reconstructed as a survival function and hazard function, which can be done in three ways. The first is a life table, the second is a Kaplan-Meier, and the third is a Cox regression analysis. From the properties of the survival analysis, the researcher was interested in applying survival analysis techniques to study survival function and hazard function of dropouts among students of the Chiang Mai University College of Arts, Media, and Technology as guides for planning education administration, students graduated and reduced the problems of departments that wasted time in management and resources in investment. In addition, the dropout rate also demonstrates the effectiveness of the department's teaching and learning management. Therefore, dropout rate is a very important consideration for education. Many factors affect students' dropout rates which result in an educational wasteland.

The objective of this study was to study the survival Function, Median Survival Time, and Hazard Rate of students and compare the Survival Function and Hazard Function patterns of students with different variables such as gender, parents' occupations, income, family status, GPA and department.

Method and Materials

This research studied the dropout rate of undergraduate students in the College of Arts, Media and Technology, Chiang Mai University. This college of Chiang Mai University contains 1 academic office and 3 main sub-departments for undergrad students. The data were obtained from the faculty admission database which sorted the data during the academic years 2016-2020. The four-year curriculum totaled 190 students. Missing data were omitted as were personal information such as name, ID and address.

The data used in the study consisted of the following variables: the dependent variable was the survival period (semester), beginning in semester 1 academic year 2016 through Semester 1 academic Year 2020 and the independent variables were gender, department, parents' occupations, income, family status and GPA. Survival analysis were used to analyze the data. This technique studied the time from the start of the study event to the occurrence of the desired event.

The research hypothesis was that the students' attributes such as gender, department, parents' occupations, income, family status and GPA have different survival functions.

Data analysis

Survival Analysis (Bundit, 2009) is generally interested in whether an event has occurred or not, such as illness, recovery or death. Therefore, the analysis is based on the percentage or rate of occurrence of such events, but it is often found that the time until the incident occurs, also known as the survival period, is more important. For example, instead of looking at whether the treatment results are dead or not, I explored how much life could be extended (survival). The information is often incomplete due to several reasons, such as the limited duration of the research. Some sample units may have occurred after the retention period. Some sample units may be missing from tracking or death, or the study event has not yet occurred, which is most often seen in medical and public health studies even though it is a natural continuation of information. However, conventional statistical analysis such as the t-test or correlation, or linear regression were incorrect because the information was incomplete. Even if you choose to analyze by percentage or rate of occurrence of the events, it would be inefficient because the information about the period is not used.

A life table is a survival analysis to predict the probability of a final event at each survival period, which can be used for survival data. The analysis results give the median time of survival. The graphs show the survival functions and hazard rates, which consist of the beginning of the period which is divided into semesters with the number of students who survived at that time, the number of student censored cases (students graduated within 4 years and those not graduating within 4 years), the number of students at risk, the number of students who drop out (students who have been dismissed and resigned) proportion of dropout students, the proportion of students surviving and the accumulated proportion of students surviving at the end of a period. It is an estimate of the probability of people who survive until the end of each period and the hazard rate ratio is the exact thickness of the cumulative ratio students who survive at the end (Cattleya, 2000).

Median Survival Time refers to the time at which the probability of survival is .0.5 If the median survival time is less than 0.5, the median duration of survival cannot be determined. This is because the dropout rate is less than %50 of the students, that is, half of the students have not dropped out during the study period (Weerasak, 2007)

Kaplan Meier uses the Log-rank test as a method of estimating the conditional probability of an event occurring, used when describing the probability of survival and hazard rate or wanting to compare the survival times of different groups with one variable. This can be done by sorting the time data and calculating survival probability and considering the Kaplan-Meier survival curve. The results showed that the survival duration of each group was not different. The Log-rank test examines the difference between the groups for a significant difference or not by Chi-squared, P-Value and indicates whether to accept or reject a hypothesis or whether there is a difference. The Kaplan-Meier Survival graph is used most frequently (Werasak, 2007).

The Cox Regression model (Duangkamol and Jutathip, 2014) studies the relationship between the duration of survival and the independent variables as the equation of hazard function.

$$h(t) = h_0(t)e^{(\beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_px_p)} \quad \text{or} \quad \ln \left[\frac{h(t)}{h_0(t)} \right] = \beta x$$

by $h_0(t)$ is Baseline Hazard

β_p is Log Hazard Ratio

x_p is Independent variable

e is base of the approximate logarithm 2.7182

Hazard Ratio (HR) is the ratio between the hazard rate of the study groups compared with the reference group.

Results

The data used for analysis are undergraduate students' data from the College of Arts, Media and Technology, Chiang Mai University cohort entering the education year 2016 for a -4year course of study with a total of 190 people. The data were devised to censored cases which consisted of students graduating within 4years/not graduating within 4years and dropout cases consisting of students dismissed/resigned. The analyses of the number and percentage of students were classified by Department of Information Technology, Department of Software Engineering and Department of Digital Game as shown in Table .1

Table .1 Number and percentage of students enrolled in the year 2016 for the -4year program classified by department.

Department	Events								Total	
	Dropout				Censored					
	Dismissed		Resigned		Did not graduate within 4years		Graduated within 4years		Number	%
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Modern management and Information Technology	9	10.96	6	7.32	0	0	67	81.72	82	100
Software Engineering	11	22.92	4	8.33	0	0	33	68.75	48	100
Animation and Game	0	0	3	5.00	0	0	57	95.00	60	100
Total	20		13				157		190	

From Table 1, it was found that students who dropped out (for reasons of being dismissed or withdrawing) 15 people in the Department of Information Technology, accounting for 18.28 percent, 15 software engineering students, 31.25 percent, and 3 digital game students accounted for 5 percent.

The results of the analysis of survival analysis by life table show the probability of survival dropout and the hazard rate of dropping out among students in the Department of Modern management and Information Technology, Department of Software Engineering, and the Department Animation and Game. The results are shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Table 2. Student Life Table of Modern management and Information Technology, Academic Year 2016.

Department	Semester	Number Entering Interval	Number Withdrawing During interval	Number Exposed to Risk	Number of Terminal Events	Proportion Terminating	Proportion Surviving	Proportion Surviving at End of interval	Proportion Density
1/2559	82	0	82.000	0	.00	1.00	1.00	.000	.00
2/2559	82	0	82.000	0	.00	1.00	1.00	.000	.00
1/2560	82	0	82.000	5	.06	.94	.94	.061	.06
2/2560	77	0	77.000	8	.10	.90	.84	.098	.11
1/2561	69	0	69.000	1	.00	1.00	.83	.012	.01
2/2561	68	0	68.000	0	.00	1.00	.83	.000	.00
1/2562	68	0	68.000	0	.00	1.00	.83	.000	.00
2/2562	68	0	68.000	0	.00	1.00	.83	.000	.00
1/2563	68	67	34.500	1	.03	.97	.81	.000	.00

From Table 2 shows that Modern management and Information Technology students had the highest hazard rate for dropping out of 0.11 in the second semester of the academic year ,2017 but there was still an %84 chance of surviving longer than the second semester of the 2017 academic year. In addition, the proportion of students who dropped out was ,%10 and the proportion of students who survived was .%90

Table 3. Student Life Table of Software Engineering, Academic year 2016.

Department	Semester	Number Entering Interval	Number Withdrawing During Interval	Number Exposed to Risk	Number of Terminal Events	Proportion Terminating	Proportion Surviving	Proportion Surviving at End of interval	Proportion Density
1/2559	48	0	48.000	0	.00	1.00	1.00	.000	.00
2/2559	48	0	48.000	0	.00	1.00	1.00	.000	.00
1/2560	48	0	48.000	8	.17	.83	.83	.167	.18
2/2560	40	0	40.000	4	.10	.90	.75	.083	.11
1/2561	36	0	36.000	3	.08	.92	.69	.063	.09
2/2561	33	0	33.000	0	.00	1.00	.69	.000	.00
1/2562	33	0	33.000	0	.00	1.00	.69	.000	.00
2/2562	33	0	33.000	0	.00	1.00	.69	.000	.00
1/2563	33	33	16.500	0	.00	1.00	.69	.000	.00

From Table 3, The software engineering students had the highest dropout hazard rate of 0.18 in the first semester of the academic year 2017 and had an 83% chance of surviving longer than the first semester of the 2017 academic year. In addition, the proportion of dropout students was 17% and the proportion of students who survived was 83%.

Table 4. Student Life Table of Animation and Game, Academic year 2016.

Department	Semester	Number Entering Interval	Number Withdrawing During Interval	Number Exposed to Risk	Number of Terminal Events	Proportion Terminating	Proportion Surviving	Proportion Surviving at End of interval	Proportion Density
1/2559	60	0	60.000	0	.00	1.00	1.00	.000	.00
2/2559	60	0	60.000	0	.00	1.00	1.00	.000	.00
1/2560	60	0	60.000	1	.02	.98	.98	.017	.02
2/2560	59	0	59.000	1	.02	.98	.97	.017	.02
1/2561	58	0	58.000	0	.00	1.00	.97	.000	.00
2/2561	58	0	58.000	1	.02	.98	.95	.017	.02
1/2562	57	0	57.000	0	.00	1.00	.95	.000	.00
2/2562	57	0	57.000	0	.00	1.00	.95	.000	.00
1/2563	57	57	28.500	0	.00	1.00	.95	.000	.00

From Table 4, The Animation and Game department students had the highest dropout hazard rate of 0.02 in the second semester of the academic year 2017 and had a 97% chance of surviving longer than the second semester of the academic year 2017. The dropout rate was 2% and the proportion of students surviving was 98%.

The dropout of undergraduate students was less than 50%. That means half of the students had not dropped out during the study period. Therefore, it was not possible to find the median of the survival period of the students in all 3 departments. From the analysis of the dropout hazard rate of students, it was found that the software engineering department had the highest hazard rate of students dropping out at 0.18, and animation and game department had the lowest hazard at 0.02.

Comparative analysis of survival functions using the Kaplan Meier Method

A comparative analysis of the survival function of students with different attributes: gender, department, occupation parent, income, family status and GPA using Kaplan Meier analysis and the Log-Rank test, to compare the survival function significance at the .05 level. There were 4 variables: gender, department, occupation parent and GPA that were significant at the 0.05 level as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Kaplan Meier Survival Analysis.

variables	Number of students	Dropout number	Number of censored	Graduation percentage	P-Value
Gender	190				.011*
Male	106	25	81	76.4	
Female	84	8	76	90.5	
Department	190				.001*
Modern management and Information Technology	82	15	67	81.7	

Software Engineering	48	15	33	68.8	
Animation and Game	60	3	57	95.0	
Parent occupation	190				.000*
Serve	48	5	43	89.6	
Private business	18	18	0	0.0	
Trade	61	0	61	100.0	
Farmers	12	3	9	75.0	
State enterprise	12	2	10	83.3	
Private employee	9	0	9	100.0	
Government employee	4	0	4	100.0	
Do not know	26	5	21	80.8	
Income					.713
Less than 10,000 baht	190	6	24	80.0	
20,000 - 10,001 baht	30	11	39	78.0	
30,000 - 20,001 baht	50	8	30	78.9	
40,000 - 30,001 baht	38	2	19	90.5	
50,000 - 40,001 baht	21	2	21	91.3	
100,000 - 50,001 baht	23	3	15	83.3	
More than 100, 000baht	18	1	9	90.0	
Family status	190				.876
Stay together	137	23	114	83.2	
Separate	9	1	8	88.9	
Divorced	29	5	24	82.8	
Parents (died)	7	2	5	71.4	
Other	8	2	6	75.0	
GPA	190				.000*
Below 1.00	4	4	0	0.0	
2.00 - 1.00	19	19	0	0.0	
2.50 - 2.01	34	5	29	85.3	
3.00 - 2.51	66	4	62	93.9	
3.50 - 3.01	49	1	48	98.0	
More than 3.50	18	0	18	100.0	

From Table 5, it was found that gender (P-Value = .011), department (P-Value = .001) occupation of parents (P-Value = .000) and GPA (P-Value = .000) had different survival functions that were statistically significant at 0.05. It was found that female students had more sensor cases than male students. Parents' occupations, such as trading and private sector and state employees, had more cases than other occupations. It was also found that the group of students with a GPA greater than 3.50 had a higher censored rate than any other range and when considering the department, it was found that students studying in animation and game department had the most censored cases compared to other departments.

Cox Regression

The analysis of the hazard function model (Hazard Rate) was the relationship between the hazard rate of dropping out among students for the academic year 2016, the -4year program, and all 4 variables: gender, department, occupation, parents and GPA as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Table of the relationship between independent variables and hazard rate of dropping out of the study, the academic year 2016, -4year curriculum.

Variables	Number of students	Hazard Rate	95% CI HR		P-Value
			Lower	Upper	
Gender	190	.878	.347	2.218	.783
Male	106				
Female	84				
Department	190				.253
Modern management and Information Technology	82	3.275	.805	13.320	
Software Engineering	48	2.788	.669	11.613	
Animation and Game	60				

Parent's occupation	190				.104
Government	48	.730	.197	2.709	
Private business	18	3.422	1.181	9.919	
Trade	61	.000	.000	4.084E+25	
Farmers	12	1.055	.243	4.569	
State enterprise	12	.807	.145	4.492	
Private employee	9	.000	.000	4.649E+71	
Government employee	4	.000	.000	1.049E+115	
Do not know	26				
GPA	190				.000*
Below 1.00	4	88317.698	.000	8.353E+50	
2.00 - 1.00	19	27686.516	.000	2.605E+50	
2.50 - 2.01	34	3967.533	.000	3.743E+49	
3.00 - 2.51	66	3028.926	.000	2.857E+49	
3.50 - 3.01	49	1825.772	.000	1.750E+49	
More than 3.50	18				

From Table 6, the results of the Cox Regression model found that the independent variables that had a statistically significant influence on the students' dropout risk at the .05 level were the GPA.

The relationship between variables and dropout hazard was analyzed by Cox regression model using variables that influenced the dropout hazard rate by the Backward method. A statistically significant dropout association with GPA at the 0.05 is shown in Table 7.

Table 7 .Table of the relationship between independent variables and hazard rate of dropping out of the study, the academic year 2016, -4year curriculum by analyzing the multiple variables using the backward method.

Variables	Number of students	B	SE	Hazard Rate	95% CI HR		P-Value
					Lower	Upper	
GPA	190						.000*
Below 1.00	4	11.389	54.013	88317.698	.000	8.353E+50	
2.00 - 1.00	19	10.229	54.010	27686.516	.000	2.605E+50	
2.50 - 2.01	34	8.286	54.012	3967.533	.000	3.743E+49	
3.00 - 2.51	66	8.016	54.011	3028.926	.000	2.857E+49	
3.50 - 3.01	49	7.510	54.020	1825.772	.000	1.750E+49	
More than 3.50	18						

From Table 7, the dropout hazard function was as follows:

$$h(t) = h_0(t)e^{(11.389gpa_1 + 10.229gpa_2 + 8.286gpa_3 + 8.016gpa_4 + 7.510gpa_5)}$$

$$\text{or } \ln \left[\frac{h(t)}{h_0(t)} \right] = 11.389gpa_1 + 10.229gpa_2 + 8.286gpa_3 + 8.016gpa_4 + 7.510gpa_5$$

From the above equation shown that when considering the B value of students with lower GPAs of 1.00, 1.00 - 2.00, 2.01 - 2.50, 2.51 - 3.00, and 3.01 - 3.50, were at a hazard rate of a dropping out compared to students with a 3.50 GPA, increased by 11.389, 10.229, 8.286, 8.016, and 7.510, respectively. In addition, when considering the hazard ratio and 95% CI, students with GPA below 1.00, 1.00 - 2.00, 2.01 - 2.50, 2.51 - 3.00, and 3.01 - 3.50 had an increased hazard rate of dropping out compared to students with a higher GPA of 3.01, 88317.698, 27686.516, 3967.533, 3028.926 and 1825.772, respectively.

Conclusion and Discussion

For the number and percentage of events of both types, dropout, and censored cases of 190 students from the academic year 2016 to the academic year 2020, of a total of 190 students, 15 students or 18.28 percent of the those in modern management and information technology department dropped out. Students in the software engineering department had the highest dropout rate, with 15, accounting for 31.25 percent of their total. The lowest dropout rate was for digital game students with 3, accounting for 5 percent.

The analysis by life table found that the students in the software engineering department had the highest hazard rate of dropping out at 0.18 in the first semester of the academic year 2017 but had an 83% chance of surviving longer than the first semester of the academic year 2017. The dropout rate was 17%, and the proportion of students surviving was 83%, whereas the digital department had the lowest hazard rate of 0.02. In addition, the median survival time of the students in all 3 departments could not be found because less than 50% of the students, had not yet occurred in the case of half of the students dropped out during the period of study.

The Kaplan Meier and Log-Rank Test showed that four independent variables: gender, department, occupation of parents, and GPA were statistically significant in relating to survival function.

The results of Cox Regression model found that the variable influencing the hazard rate of dropout hazard rate of undergraduate students was the GPA which corresponds to research by Han and Ganges (1995), that a field of study does not influence student dropout hazard rate, but GPA does influence student dropout.

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